
RESSISSTANCE LITERATURE: "THE HUNGER GAMES" BY SUSANNE COLLINS

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Abstract.

Introduction. "Hunger Games" is the first book of HUNGER GAMES trilogy which is best-seller book known worldwide. This action packed and thought provoking trilogy includes a lot of genres in it, like young-adult fiction, science fiction, thriller, dystopian fiction, adventure. However, the genre of the book is mostly dystopia and adventure science fiction.

Research methods. In the research method main and major characters have been analysed through depiction, characterization and delineation of inner and outer features of Katniss Everdeen, Peeta Mellark, Haymitch Abernathy, Effie Trinket etc.

Results and discussions. The ideas in the book are confusing. The reader must read them through the lines. Distrust covers whole novel, individual cannot trust the details and should be cautious. One may get confused trying to understand whether main character is protagonist or is she just over thinking the and president of nation is just silly man loving to live in comfort.

Conclusion. We totally agree that the title is perfect fit for both trilogy and the first book. For the reason that I think author wanted to show not only annual Games where people in districts watch how their children die, kill each other, try their best to survive; but also the "Games" going on beyond the Arena. The political Games. Therefore, author wanted to show that both games have things in common.

Key words.

American prose, young-adult fiction, thriller, dystopian fiction, adventure, science fiction

Introduction.

An American author and television writer Suzanne Collins was born on 10th August 1962 in Hartford, United States of America. For the reason that her father was Lieutenant Colonel they always kept moving from one place to another and her childhood was spent in eastern United States. She devoted her life to the Art.

Graduating Art school in Birmingham, studying bachelors at art in Indiana university and earning Master's at art in New York university. She started working as a children's writer in Television Shows. And wrote books for children[1,3].

Her most famous bestseller is Hunger Games books (trilogy). "Hunger Games" is the first book of HUNGER GAMES trilogy which is best-seller book known worldwide. This action packed and thought provoking trilogy includes a lot of genres in it, like young-adult fiction, science fiction, thriller, dystopian fiction, adventure. However, the genre of book I am writing about, which is the first one, is mostly dystopia and adventure science fiction.

The reason of Hunger Games to be dystopian is apparent from the name of the country, Panem. The author called the country like that not because she liked it, but for the reason that Panem is the word derived from Latin which means "bread. It refers to the fact that the residents of the country are starving and have little things to eat [10,4]. And also, should be noted that gladiatorial games existed in Ancient Rome that were called panem et circences (bread and circuses) it bears the resemblances of the games in the book which is called hunger games. The phrase refers to the Roman Caesars' strategy of quelling public discontent by providing the people with plenty of food and entertainment. It is defined as a science fiction due to the newest futuristic technologies and settings like Hovercraft and Teleporting devices. The author, Suzanne Collins is trying to describe the situations of the authorities being rude and playing with lives of residents; the way some people forgetting the world around, how authorities make them not to pay attention to the poverty and violence going on around. The totalitarian government of Panem is who holds all the power over the districts. The citizens have no say over their lives or what the government will impose on them. The message of the novel is that not any violence can succeed due to the reason that every brutality leaves scars on whatever it can be, the scars cause revolution which is inevitable. Worthy to mention, no revolution blows over without personal sacrifice. And only patience and love can ease the pain of it

Atmosphere: The tone of narration begins to be scary and dark. This is to be kept whole novel. The brutal atmosphere could have made people serious and dangerous, however they all keep on together. People knowingly try not to change as they know that it is the only thing Capitol, the authorities, is waiting for. It is clearly shown in the words of one of the main characters - Peeta Mellark:

"I don't want them to change me in there. Turn me into some kind of monster that I'm not." [1,234]

Peeta recognizes this atmosphere and chooses to preserve his own identity, regardless of the games' atmosphere. He is mainly concerned with how the environment will impact who he actually is as a human being. The atmosphere created in The Hunger Games is one of desperation and debasement. Materials and method. Major character: Katniss Everdeen Other names - Catnip, Girl on Fire, Sweetheart, The Mockingjay, The Victor of the 74th Hunger Games. Author wanted her to be the main protagonist in the novel, however I consider Peeta to be the one. Because Katniss doesn't try to fight for improvement of the world she is living in, she only wants to stay alive as well as save her family. Katniss is a girl living in the 12th district - the poorest area in Panem, she has a typical characteristic of her area of Seam. She is described to have "straight black hair, olive skin, and grey eyes" she makes her hair a single braid at her back. She is thin of normal height, but strong for her size, as she has to go hunting with Gale to outskirts of district 12 so that she can feed her family. Her father died when she was 11 after which mother fell into deep depression and all the responsibilities including taking care of her small sister, mother; finding food for family, doing all the house chores were left on the shoulders of Katniss. During the time of Hunger Games she was 17 years old.

Katniss owns a character of survivalist that makes her strong, independent and lethal and allow her to think outside the box. She is the one who puts the lives of others' first and even ready to sacrifice her own only to preserve others'. An example for that may be the culmination situation where everything begins which is when Katniss volunteered to go to the fatal games for her sister Prim. Because she had to go through so many hardships and almost all her time is spent to feed her family she appears to be strongly distrustful and fails to understand some social cues. For example she doesn't recognize Gale's hints at his growing affection for her, or when she fails to realize that she and Madge Undersee are actually close friends as well as when she threatens Peeta for not being honest and till the end of book she doesn't realize that Peeta was not acting or lying.

Peeta Mellark Other names - The Boy with Bread, The Baker's Boy, Lover Boy, Star-crossed Lover. I consider him to be the real protagonist in the novel. For the reason that he tries to keep his real self and not change as Capitol wants him to. Peeta works in the family business of bakery. His name itself means the type of bread "pita". He is of "medium height, stocky build" and has "ashy blond hair that falls in waves over his forehead." And has blue eyes. He is "broad-shouldered and strong." He is 17 years old and described to be kind,

generous and charming. Firstly, because of his sense of humor, Katniss do not take him seriously but then she understands his determination and seriousness.

Haymitch Abernathy stock character. Haymitch is only one Hunger Games winner of 12th district and the mentor of 74th Hunger Games' 12th districts' tributes. He is harsh, indelicate, manipulative and mostly severely drunk; paunchy and middle-aged. However despite his being drunk he can control his condition. As he says to Peeta and Katniss – let him drink as much as he wants and he will be sober enough to help them. Effie Trinket “Happy Hunger Games, and may the odds be ever in your favor.” Effie is escort of 12th district, stock character, born and raised in the capitol, not understanding the political views of Katniss and Peeta she enjoys watching Hunger Games just like other residents of Capitol. Her colorful clothes and wigs make her unforgettable. She is given as a model of wealth and power of the government and that is the reason of her being silly woman who places a good deal of emphasis on etiquette and propriety.

Minor characters: Primrose Everdeen: Prim was totally opposite of Katniss both physically and by character despite the fact that they were sisters. She was blonde and had a talent of healing. She was naïve and gentle. Gale Hawthorne: Gale owns the same character and appearance as Katniss, having olive skin, black hair and grey eyes. From early age they hunted together and became best friends. Cinna: To me Cinna doesn't seem to be Capitol-raised because at the moment when everyone congratulated Katniss he just said that he is sorry that she became a tribute. For his being not like Capitol people Katniss thinks that he is not experienced enough, however he says that he asked to be 12th district stylist himself. Rue: Rue was the youngest tribute in the games, being 12 years old (just like Katniss's sister). She looked like an Afro American girl with thick dark curly hair. She was the ally of Katniss at the beginning of the games, due to the reason that she brought back the memories of Prim to Katniss.

President Snow is an antagonist in the novel. He is the ruler of the Panem. Cruel, manipulative and cold. He is the small man with white hair; his breath smells like a blood and roses he always holds, because he has illness of bleeding sores.

Results.

The first book of trilogy – The Hunger Games is about nation of Panem located in a place once known as North America. Panem is shining Capitol surrounded by 12 districts. The districts are kept in fear and forced to serve to the Capitol. Starving people have no courage to go against the Capitol that forces every district to send a

male and female tribute of the age from 12 to 18 in order to participate in the annual Hunger Games, a game till death being transmitted on live TV.

Katniss Everdeen at her sixteen's, understands that she is pushing herself to a death sentence by volunteering to take her sister's place as a tribute. However it doesn't mean that she is going to die as she is a good hunter and survival is her second nature. During the acts she opens for herself new people, especially people of Capitol and their trouble less lives.

She tries her best to win the games and she will be able to do it. Which means the end of the novel/idea, but beginning of another forcing the reader to starve to read the second book of trilogy.

Discussion.

The actions of the novel take place in a country of Panem which rose from the ashes of place known as North America. The nation included capital city (the Capitol) surrounded by 13 districts. However durable civil war and the uprising of the Districts against the Capitol called the "Dark Days" made Capitol destroy 13th district and impose annual Hunger games - fight to death - to remind the Districts that this uprising must never be repeated. Panem is the word derived from Latin which means "bread". Gladiatorial games existed in Ancient Rome that were called panem et circences (bread and circuses) it bears the resemblances of the games in the book which is called hunger games. The phrase refers to the Roman Caesars' strategy of quelling public discontent by providing the people with plenty of food and entertainment.

Within Panem, the settings for this book include District 12, the Capitol and the Arena. District 12, to be exact, the Seam is the place where main character is from. The Seam is considered to be the poorest area where coal miners work and the city itself is covered with the dust of coal. The Capitol is the capital city where all the wealthiest people live, but to be wealthy is not enough to live there - one must be born in Capitol. When it comes to Arena, it is the venue made up artificially where all the tributes brought and made fight with each other to death.

However when it comes to time, it is worthy to note that nothing is mentioned about it. Only information is that author used Gregorian calendar to estimate time. Also that the actions took part in post-American time - in the future.

The most exhilarating, full of emotions part for me was is the end of part 1 and the beginning of part 2. The moment when Caesar asks Peeta if he has a girlfriend back home. Surprisingly Peeta says that he had a long-term crush on Katniss. i was filled with emotions when I read that part and tried to read faster to find out what

will happen next. I never read any part of book repeatedly, but this part was surely an exceptional one. However, the response of Katniss was much more interesting that I did not know to laugh or to cry. Author made me doubt my thoughts when Katniss blamed Peeta lying to Caesar for his own sake – to collect sponsors.

The part from the novel is amazingly worthy to restate:

“What does it matter?” says the mayor. He’s looking at me with a pained expression on his face. He doesn’t know me really, but there’s a faint recognition there. I am the girl who brings the strawberries. The girl his daughter might have spoken of on occasion. The girl who five years ago stood huddled with her mother and sister, as he presented her, the oldest child, with a medal of valor. A medal for her father, vaporized in the mines. Does he remember that? “What does it matter?” he repeats gruffly. “Let her come forward.”

Prim is screaming hysterically behind me. She’s wrapped her skinny arms around me like a vice. “No, Katniss! No! You can’t go!”

“Prim, let go,” I say harshly, because this is upsetting me and I don’t want to cry. When they televise the replay of the reappings tonight, everyone will make note of my tears, and I’ll be marked as an easy target. A weakling. I will give no one that satisfaction. “Let go!”

I can feel someone pulling her from my back. I turn and see Gale has lifted Prim off the ground and she’s thrashing in his arms. “Up you go, Catnip,” he says, in a voice he’s fighting to keep steady, and then he carries Prim off toward my mother. I steel myself and climb the steps.

2) “Peeta sighs. “Well, there is this one girl. I’ve had a crush on her ever since I can remember. But I’m pretty sure she didn’t know I was alive until the reaping.”

Sounds of sympathy from the crowd. Unrequited love they can relate to.

“She have another fellow?” asks Caesar.

“I don’t know, but a lot of boys like her,” says Peeta.

“So, here’s what you do. You win, you go home. She can’t turn you down then, eh?” says Caesar encouraging-ly.

“I don’t think it’s going to work out. Winning...won’t help in my case,” says Peeta.

“Why ever not?” says Caesar, mystified.

Peeta blushes beet red and stammers out. “Because...because...she came here with me.”

I can’t stop looking at Rue, smaller than ever, a baby animal curled up in a nest of netting. I can’t bring myself to leave her like this. Past harm, but seeming

utterly defenseless. To hate the boy from District 1, who also appears so vulnerable in death, seems inadequate. It's the Capitol I hate, for doing this to all of us.

Gale's voice is in my head. His ravings against the Capitol no longer pointless, no longer to be ignored. Rue's death has forced me to confront my own fury against the cruelty, the injustice they inflict upon us. But here, even more strongly than at home, I feel my impotence. There's no way to take revenge on the Capitol. Is there?

Then I remember Peeta's words on the roof. "Only I keep wishing I could think of a way to ... to show the Capital they don't own me. That I'm more than just a piece in their Games." And for the first time, I understand what he means.

I want to do something, right here, right now, to shame them, to make them accountable, to show the Capitol that whatever they do or force us to do there is a part of every tribute they can't own. That Rue was more than a piece in their Games.

This part was really interesting and full of emotions. Due to Peeta unexpectedly announcing Katniss to be his crush from long ago [14, 381]. Also this pulls the reader into a doubt of whether he is telling truth or is it his new strategy to draw attention of the sponsors so that they will be interested on him more and invest more money. As money is needed during the fight in Arena for the medicines, weapons, or food to be delivered by the coach when needed.

Generally, the book was very interesting. I should note that I watched the film before reading it and I was pleased to find the book to be far more fascinating than the movie. I can say that I have never read a book more invocatory than this. This book makes reader to experience all existing feelings. Tells people to be grateful for the government that doesn't impose annual death games to teach a lesson. Shortly teaches to appreciate peace; as well as motivating to not stay calm and live in patience in the buildup world, but start to act, flounder to fight for better life.

Author states that the main theme of the book is survival [12, 56]. I totally agree with her regarding the theme of the book. Because in harsh and merciless rule of president it is clearly visible that people have to take care about themselves in the world where pors are being poorer and dying while the richest ones are enjoying life as much as they can. Rich people, living in an artificial world have no idea of the other districts lifestyles [17, 137]. However, in districts people are starving to death and only the people with survival abilities may keep living.

The ideas in the book are confusing. The reader must read them through the lines. Distrust covers whole novel, individual cannot trust the details and should be cautious. One may get confused trying to understand whether main character is

protagonist or is she just over thinking the and president of nation is just silly man loving to live in comfort.

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The harsh, cruel government controls Katniss and people of 12 districts just like 24 tributes being controlled by Gamemakers in Arena. It resembles that the whole life in this novel is very much a game – the Hunger Game.

Even though I consider the title of the book to be perfect, We would suggest SURVIVE IN GAMES as an alternative variation. Nevertheless, we would never have agreed to change the title of trilogy.

LIST OF USED LITERATURE:

1. Collins S. “The Hunger Games” (the first book of trilogy). New York: 2008 –P.384
2. Collins S. The Ballad of Songbirds and Snakes New York: 2020 –P.331
3. Collins S. Catching Fire. New York: Scholastic inc, 2009 –P.364
4. Collins S. Mockingjay. New York: Scholastic inc, 2009 –P.364
5. Collins S. Gregor the Overlander New York: Scholastic inc, 2009 –P.352
6. Collins S. Gregor and the Prophecy of Bane. New York: Scholastic inc, 2009 –P.344
7. Collins S Gregor and the Curse of the Warmbloods. New York: Scholastic inc, 2005 –P.355
8. Collins S Gregor and the Marks of Secret New York: Scholastic inc, 2006 –P.263
9. Collins S Gregor and the Code of Claw. New York: Scholastic inc, 2007 –P.397
10. Mentz S. Romance for sale in early modern England: the rise of prose fiction. Routledge. 2017
11. Mekhriniso Musinovna Rakhmatova, & Nilufar Furkatovna Botirova. (2022). NEW APPROACHES IN LATINO AMERICAN POETRY: CHICANO

POETRY. Open Access Repository, 8(04), 92-94.
<https://oarepo.org/index.php/oa/article/view/549>

12. Mehriniso Musinovna Rakhmatova, & Dilnoza Ilkhomovna Inoyatova. (2022). CONCEPTUAL AND FIGURATIVE STRUCTURE OF THE CONCEPT OF "UGLINESS". Open Access Repository, 8(04), 58-61.
<https://oarepo.org/index.php/oa/article/view/556>

13. Mehriniso Raxmatova Musinovna, & Mekhriniso Charieva Jakhonovna. (2022). SOCIO-CULTURAL PRAGMATICS AS A METHOD OF PEDAGOGICALLY INTERPRETING INTERCULTURAL EXPERIENCES. Conferencea, 148-150.
<https://conferencea.org/index.php/conferences/article/view/322>

14. Musinovna, R. M. (2021). AESTHETIC VALUE IN ENGLISH, UZBEK AND TAJIK NATIONAL CULTURES. *Academicia Globe: Inderscience Research*, 2 (05), 380-389.
https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=w7L-jhQAAAAJ&citation_for_view=w7L-jhQAAAAJ:zYLM7Y9cAGgC

15. Musinovna, R. M. (2022). Academic Integrity: Teaching and Learning Challenges. *Integration Conference on Integration of Pragmalinguistics, Functional Translation Studies and Language Teaching Processes*, 30-33.
<https://conferenceseries.info/index.php/online/article/view/35>

16. Rakhmatova, M. (2022). Академическая честность и плагиат: проблемы воспитания. ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu.Uz), 15(15).
https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=w7L-jhQAAAAJ&citation_for_view=w7L-jhQAAAAJ:MXK_kJrjxJIC

17. Rakhmatova, M. M. "Cross-cultural understanding of values in language. *Міжнародний науковий журнал Інтернаука*,(1 (1)), 136-137." (1908).
<http://www.inter-nauka.com/uploads/public/15058932524023.pdf#page=137>

18. Rakhmatova Mekhriniso Muhsinovna, and Usmonov Amon Aminovich. "THE IMPLEMENTATION OF CORPUS-BASED TECHNIQUES TO ANALYZE LITERARY WORKS". *Open Access Repository*, vol. 8, no. 04, Apr. 2022, pp. 88-91
https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=w7L-jhQAAAAJ&citation_for_view=w7L-jhQAAAAJ:kNdYIx-mwKoC

a. Rakhmatova M.M., and Ziyodullayeva M.E.. "THE WAYS OF TEACHING HOW TO SPEAK AND THE ROLE OF TEACHER IN THAT PROCESS" World science, vol. 3, no. 4 (4), 2015, pp. 43-45. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/the-ways-of-teaching-how-to-speak-and-the-role-of-teacher-in-that-process>